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Impact of ultra-confinement on dilation of polymer films under supercritical carbon dioxide

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Introduction: Since last two decades the use of supercritical fluids such as supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO₂) has emerged as a leading alternative to toxic organic solvents in polymer processing and synthesis, reactor clean up and preparation of pharmaceutical products. While the effect of CO₂ has been studied extensively in thick polymer films (thickness $d > 100$ nm) since long back and more recently in thin films ($20 \text{ nm} < d < 100 \text{ nm}$), to the best of our knowledge there is a lack of report on the dilation behaviour of ultra-confined polymer films under scCO₂ in the thickness regime below 20 nm, especially down to 3 nm [1]. Here, we report the dilation process of various types of confined polymers (PS-PEB-PS, PS and PBMA) ultrathin films (d ranges from 3 to 110 nm) under scCO₂. The swelling is found to be dependent on the confinement of polymer films.

Methods: Polymer ultrathin films of different thicknesses ($d \approx 3$ nm to 110 nm) were prepared by adjusting the concentration of polymer-solvent (e.g. toluene) solutions. Films were deposited by spin-coating (Apex Instruments) these solutions at 2000 rpm for 1 min onto cleaned Si(100) substrates. The Si surfaces (of size $\approx 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$) were made hydrophilic by immersing them in a mixed solution of ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH, Sigma-Aldrich, 25%), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, Acros Organics, 35%), and Milli-Q water (H₂O:NH₄OH:H₂O₂ = 2:1:1, by volume) for 10 min at 100 °C. XRR measurements were carried to investigate the structure of polymer ultrathin films before and after CO₂ exposition followed by their relaxation.

Results & Discussions: Relatively thinner films ($d \approx 3$ nm) exhibit higher swelling ($> 100\%$) compared to the thicker ones ($< 20\%$) [1,2]. Rapid release of CO₂ during depressurization in the process of scCO₂ exposition leads to swollen structures [2], resulting in low-density polymer ultrathin films where free volume is enlarged and/or nanometer-scale sized porosity is significantly (13 – 25 %) introduced. These effects alter polymer to polymer which having large difference in T_g and chemical groups [2]. In addition, relaxation process is found to be extremely slow until the temperature reaches to glass transition temperature (T_g) [1]. Hence this swollen structure could easily be preserved. Such porous polymers are ideal to develop novel highly gas permeable membranes for gas filtration that selectively allow specific gas molecules. Furthermore, scCO₂ acts as a plasticiser that increases the mobility of polymer chains by reducing the cumulative intermolecular forces among the polymer chain segments.

Conclusions: We have carried out XRR measurements to investigate the dilation and relaxation characteristics of homo (PS and PBMA) and triblock copolymer (PS-PEB-PS) films having different thicknesses exposed to scCO₂ and compared with each other. In all these cases, thinner films exhibit a large swellability in opposition to thicker films due to densification of the former. A general relation between density, thickness and swellability of polymer thin film is established. A significant difference in swellability and absolute swelling, which are dominant in PBMA, is encountered. The presence of specific interaction of CO₂ with the carbonyl groups of PBMA, unlike PS and PS-PEB-PS, allows large mobility of polymer chains in scCO₂ solvent which results in highly swollen films.

Keywords: *Supercritical Carbon Dioxide, Dilation, Confinement, X-ray reflectivity.*

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